

JAPANESE EDUCATION SYSTEM AND ASSESSMENT STANDARDS

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Abstract. *Educational assessment aims to accurately reflect student learning outcomes and improve teacher instruction. It also plays a vital role in enabling students to reflect on their learning for future learning. This article examines the education system, higher education, and assessment standards in Japan.*

Keywords: *Japanese Education System, Japanese National, Public and Private Universities, Chosasho Transcripts.*

The main part. The Japanese education system uses a "six-three-three-four" system, which includes six years of elementary school (for children aged 6–12) and three years of middle school. 13–15 years), a three-year secondary school (i.e. upper secondary or high school for 16–18-year-olds) and a four-year university. Nine years of primary and upper secondary school are compulsory. According to the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology, a high percentage of high school graduates (98.4% in 2013) attended secondary or related schools, about half (53.2 %) received higher education. There are some schools that do not follow the six-three-three-four system, such as the schools of medicine, pharmacy, and dentistry.

As for entrance exams, public primary and secondary schools generally do not use them. Since high school and university are not compulsory, they conduct entrance exams.

Private education plays an important role in higher education. As of 2013, only 1.0 percent of elementary schools, 7.3 percent of middle schools, and 26.5 percent of high schools are private. In contrast, of Japan's 782 universities, 77.5% are private, the remaining 11.0% are national, and 11.5% are other public (prefectural or municipal) universities.

There are three main types of universities in Japan: national, public, and private. The academic year in Japan traditionally runs from April to the following March, and so does most universities.

- National Universities - Funded by the Japanese government and generally regarded as the most prestigious institutions in the country. There are about 86 in total, including the University of Tokyo - one of the top 30 universities in the world.

- State universities - receive funds from local governments (city or prefecture). This means that although they are less prestigious than national universities, they often have strong ties to their communities. There are about 100 public universities in Japan.

- Private universities - make up the majority of universities in Japan, there are currently over 600 of them. Since they are not funded by the government, they often have to charge higher fees. However, this means that they have more freedom and flexibility in their curricula and admissions policies.

There are a number of other types of post-secondary institutions in Japan, all of which offer qualifications that are not equivalent to a full degree. These include junior colleges, specialized

training colleges, and technical colleges. They often focus on vocational education, which means that the courses there are aimed at preparing students for a specific type of work.

After World War II, there were two major debates in the Japanese education sector about the overall decline in academic achievement, which resulted in the introduction of two national assessments of academic achievement. The first debate began with criticism of the first training course introduced in 1948 (see above). This course of study focuses on an empiricism-based educational system. It has been criticized for causing a drop in academic achievement. This decline in achievement led to the introduction of national assessments of academic achievement. The Ministry of Education conducted an academic survey of a nationwide sample of students in 1956 and a full survey of all high school students in 1961.

The above-mentioned post-war national assessment of academic ability continued until 1964, when it was suspended during a period of political controversy. At the time, the Japan Teachers' Union had considerable power and opposed many of the Ministry of Education's policies, arguing that the ministry had introduced centralism. The union was concerned that such national assessments were being used by the government to control the content of education and force a poor educational curriculum on students.

Every three years since 2000, the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Mathematics, First Language (L1) Reading and Science. Japan's lower rankings than in the past have created a sense of crisis in academic achievement. The PISA ranking also came as a surprise to the Finnish education system, which until 2009 was ranked high. Many Japanese educational researchers visited Finland to study their educational philosophy and methods, and published books to spread knowledge of Finnish methods. The Japanese government believed that an education that would enable students to achieve higher PISA scores without critically examining the content or format of the test was ideal. Such trends show the dependence of the public on the results of "internationally established tests".

However, the Japanese public seems to be applying a double standard. In Shanghai's 2009 PISA ranking, several Japanese researchers visited the area or recognized Shanghai's education. One reason, the researchers say, is that it leads to multiple insights because China and Japan have similar cultures of testing and learning, with competitive entrance exams and candidates studying hard for success.

Unlike many countries, Japanese higher education does not have a standardized grading system. However, most universities use a four-point scale of A, B, C, and F. Only the most exceptional work is graded A, and F is considered failing. Students who receive the latter can retake the exam or assignment.

In addition to the four-point scale, many universities now use the GPA system. This gives students a numerical score of 0.0 to 4.0, comparable to the system used in countries such as America.

When it comes to numbers, it's also important to consider tuition costs.

When a student wishes to transfer from secondary education to higher education in Japan, high school grades and records of various academic and other activities are accepted as one of the sources of entrance screening. Applicants submit a transcript form to HEI as part of their application documents. Chosho is compiled by the student's senior high school based on guidance notes. Chosho transcripts include academic grades, attendance, and special events during senior high school. Academic grades are graded for each subject and course on a scale of 1 to 5, with 5 being the highest grade. Each higher education institution defines its own academic assessment

standards and methods. Universities are required by law to clearly communicate assessment standards to students in advance.

The grading scale for different higher education institutions is different. For example, the 5-point rating scale is in Japanese “秀 (shu), 優 (yu), 良 (ryo), 可 (ka), 不可 (fuka)” or in letter grades “S, A, B, C, F” can use from examples of 4-step rating scales: “優 (yu), 良 (ry), 可 (k), 不可 (fuka), “A, B, C, D” or “5, 4, 3, 1”.

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